

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL SCRUB ON FACE

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ABSTRACT :

Herbal face scrubs have become increasingly popular in recent years due to their ability to improve skin health and are available at a low cost. For the healthy and nourish skin periodic cleansing requires which removes the dirt, dead skin, sebum other secretion Extends the skin and their appendix by chemical topical application. This is useful for making skin charming and beautiful. Cosmetic plays very important role in everyone's life to make joyful skin. Nowadays herbal cosmeceuticals are in demand due to less or no side effect. Hebalcosmeceutical usually contain plant part which posses antimicrobial, antiaging, antiacne, antioxidant property. The number of research has studied rice benefit namely good nutritional value, resistance to high blood pressure. The problem like blackhead, whiteheads, acne might irritate nowadays here scrubbing become useful. For the healthy skin there is need of cleansing, removing dirt and debris. The current work is based on the formulation and evaluation of herbal facial scrub by using herbal drugs and evaluation is done by using various parameters. Thus prepared formulation use effectively to show the cleansing and glowing action. Using rice flour, lemon juice, Multanimitti, Neem Powder, Haldi, Tulsi, Mint, Xantham Gum, Gram flour, Sodium Benzoate, Shikakai and Water, we Created formulation for scrubbing and whitening. These formulation were then tested for various parameter, including Physical appearance, Homogeneity, Extrudability, Spreadability, Irritability, Washability, Grittiness, Foamability, Viscosity, Stability, Consistency.

KEYWORD: Scrubbing, cleansing, herbal, Antiacne, Whitening.

1. INTRODUCTION:

The body's largest organ is the skin. It acts as the body's defence mechanism. Skin acts as a wrapper-like barrier for protection. Maintaining everything below. Skin is a sensory organ that shows a person's health.

Definition of cosmetic: Cosmetics are defined as articles meant to be poured, rubbed, sprinkled, sprayed, or injected into the human body for cleansing, beautifying, boosting attractiveness, or altering appearance without harming structure or function under the terms of the Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act. [1]

Cosmetics are described as products that are used to cleanse, beautify, promote beauty, or alternate one's appearance. Different herbs have been utilised for cleaning, beautifying, and managing them since ancient times. The skin of the face is the largest part of the body and reflects an individual's health. [2]

Cosmeceuticals are a marketer's dream, allowing for the incorporation of an infinite number of active ingredients obtained from a wide range of natural and synthetic sources into skincare products. Vitamins, antioxidants, minerals, herbs, hormones, anti-inflammatories, anti-depressants, mood-altering aromas (aromatherapy), and even exotic ingredients like placenta and amniotic fluid have all been utilized in cosmeceuticals. [3]

Natural beauty blessings and cosmetics aid in the presentation and enhancement of a person's beauty and personality. People nowadays prefer natural foods, herbal treatments, and natural healing procedures for a healthy lifestyle. Herbal cosmetics are formulations with phytochemicals from various plant sources that regulate skin function and give essential nutrients for healthy skin. Herbal cosmetics are natural plants and their products that are utilized in cosmetic preparations for their aromatic value. Because there is a widespread assumption that chemical-based cosmetics are harmful, herbal goods have sparked a desire for natural products and natural extracts in cosmetics formulations. [4]

ANATOMY OF SKIN:

The integumentary system is the largest organ and composed of skin, hair, nails, and glands. The epidermis regenerates with new cells every 28 days. This layer measures the thickness of 0.05 to 0.1 mm.

A) Epidermis

B) Dermis

c) Subcutaneous tissue

A cosmetic product called a facial scrub is used to hydrate, exfoliate, and clean the skin on the face. The three types of skin are sensitive, oily, and dry skin. Those with dry skin should wash their faces with a moisturizer-containing cleanser and then apply moisturizer. Gently scrubbing sensitive skin is recommended. To avoid clogged pores and to keep the skin's oil production in control, oily skin needs a scrub that exfoliates deeply. [5]

There is no specific procedure in the preparation of rice scrub compared to other products; it is a pure natural handcrafted facial scrub, so there is no specific technique. So all we have to do now is combine the various components in a precise and discrete manner until we get a perfect mixture, which we may call a scrub. There are various forms of scrub that we might refer to as alternatives. When dead skin cells accumulate on the surface of your skin, your complexion might become bland. That's where exfoliation, specifically the use of a face scrub, might help. When you remove dead skin cell buildup from the surface of your skin, your complexion can improve. [6]

Benefits of scrubbing skin : [7]

- 1. Helps in removing dead cells:** Facial or body scrubs are the cosmetic which goes beyond surface level to remove dead skin and reveal the healthy glowing skin below.
- 2. Free the skin from flakes:** Loss of upper layer of skin (epidermis) is called as flaky skin. It gives rise to dry patches. Scrubbing your skin can help you to deal with flaky skin effectively.
- 3. Deep cleaning of skin:** Scrubbing your skin helps skin to get free from dirt, oil and sweat. Other cleansing like face wash facial cleansers cannot clean the skin.
4. Thoroughly removing dust accumulated in the course of the skin, scrubbing does this work effectively.
- 5. Clears blemishes:** Accumulation of dead skin, can block the pores of skin and causes blemishes. Scrubbing frequently helps to remove dead skin and clears blemishes.
- 6. Gives glow to Skin and Smooth texture:** Scrubbing actually helps to give glow and smooth texture to skin.
- 7. Remove the acne scars:** As scrubbing used to remove dead skin cells, it also remove the acne scars from skin.
- 8. Promotes hydration of skin:** Facial scrubs contains moisturizing agents and hydrating agents. Exfoliation of skin helps to absorb moisture and it leaves our skin with filling soft
- 9. Reduces stress:** Exfoliation or scrubbing the skin gives good massage, which gives relaxing feeling and reduces stress.

Ideal features of a face scrub : [8]

1. It must be non-toxic, mildly abrasive as well as non-sticky.
2. Dead skin cells and grime must be removed.
3. It must be non-irritating.
4. It must have minute grit in it.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS :

Sr.No	Ingredient	Figure	Use
1	RICE FLOUR		Remove dead skin cell, dirt
2	LEMON JUICE		Astringent and Antiseptic
3	Multani Mitti		Remove blackhead and whitehead
4	Neem Powder		Antiaging, Humectant
5	Honey		Moisturizer, Nourish skin

6	Tulsi	A photograph showing fresh green Tulsi leaves on a wooden surface next to a small white bowl filled with a fine green powder.	Antiacne, Clear the skin
7	Mint	A photograph of a dark purple bowl filled with green powder, surrounded by fresh green mint leaves.	Cleans pore and slough off any dead skin cell
8	Xantham Gum	A photograph of a small pile of light-colored, fine powder.	Gelling agent, Provide high viscosity
9	Gram Flour	A photograph showing a pile of yellow gram flour on a wooden surface, with yellow lentils scattered below it.	Remove all the dead and dirt skin cell from your face
10	Sodium Benzoate	A photograph of a white, fine powder in a white bowl.	Prevent yeast, mold, fungus from forming
11	Shikakai	A photograph of several dark brown, irregular pieces of Shikakai.	Foaming agent and cleansing agent

12	Rose Oil		Flavourant, Protect against sun damage
13	Walnut Shell		Scrubbing agent

METHOD OF COLLECTION:

1. Collection of Rice Flour:

Fresh rice was collected from a shop and thoroughly washed with water to remove impurities. The cleaned rice was then dried properly and ground using a grinder to obtain a fine powder. The powdered rice was passed through sieve number 60 to achieve a uniform particle size suitable for formulation preparation.

2. Collection of Neem powder

Fresh neem leaves were collected from a garden and washed thoroughly to remove dirt and other impurities. The leaves were then shade-dried for about 7 days to preserve their natural properties. After complete drying, the leaves were ground using a grinder to obtain a fine powder. The powder was then passed through sieve number 60 to achieve a uniform particle size for further use.

3. Collection of Mint powder

Fresh mint leaves were collected from a local vegetable shop and washed thoroughly to remove any impurities. The leaves were then shade-dried for about 5 days to retain their natural aroma and properties. After drying, the leaves were ground using a grinder to obtain a fine powder. The powdered material was then passed through sieve number 60 to ensure uniform particle size for further use.

4. Collection of Tulsi powder

Fresh tulsi leaves were collected from a local garden and washed thoroughly to remove dust and impurities. The leaves were then shade-dried for about 4–5 days to maintain their natural constituents. After complete drying, the leaves were ground using a grinder to obtain a fine powder. The powder was then passed through sieve number 60 to achieve a uniform particle size for further formulation use.

5. Collection of other ingredient

Lemon juice, Multanimitti, Honey, gram floor, shikakai was collected from shop. , Sodium Benzoate, XanthamGum , Rose oil were collected from college laboratory.

Table 1: Formulation Table

Sr.No	Ingredient	F1	F2	F3	F4
1	Rice Flour	2 gm	3 gm	2 gm	2.2 gm
2	Lemon Juice	3 ml	3 ml	4 ml	4 ml
3	MultaniMitti	2.3 gm	2 gm	4 gm	2.3 gm
4	Neem Powder	1 gm	2 gm	1 gm	1 gm
5	Honey	3 ml	2 ml	3 ml	4 ml
6	Tulsi	2 gm	1 gm	1gm	1 gm
7	Mint	1.2 gm	1gm	0.5 gm	1 gm
8	Xantham Gum	2 gm	2.5 gm	2 gm	2 gm
9	Gram Flour	3.5 gm	3 gm	3 gm	3.5 gm
10	Sodium Benzoate	2 gm	2 gm	1.5 gm	2 gm
11	Shikakai	2 gm	2gm	1.5 gm	2 gm
12	Rose Oil	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml	1 ml
13	Walnut Shell	2gm	2gm	2gm	2 gm
14	Water	qs	qs	qs	qs

METHOD OF PREPARATION :

Step1.

Preparation of gel In a beaker, soak the specified amount of Xantham Gum with enough water. Using a petri plate, close the beaker. Set aside the beaker for 24 hours. Triethamoline was added at the end to correct the pH

Step 2.

Preparation of active ingredients Weigh all ingredients as given in formulation table.

Mix them uniformly using mortar and pestle.

Step 3.

Add prepared gel The produced gel was added to the active ingredient mixture and mixed. The produced Formulation was then assessed utilizing several parameters.

Step 4.

Using mechanical stirrer, add water to mixture.

Evaluation parameter:

- 1. Physical Appearance:** Visual observation was made of the formulation's physical appearance. Color, aroma, character, and consistency were all observed during this test.
- 2. Homogeneity:** The homogeneity of the formulation was carefully inspected. To measure pH of the scrub component, digital pH meter was employed.
- 3. Extrudability:** Extrudability was measured by amount of time needed for the sample to entirely extrude from the container or sample amount/time required.
- 4. Determination of spreadability of scrub:** The scrub was lightly sprinkled on top of the gel. On top of it, a 20g wooden weight was put. Both the length of time the brush took to spread and the area it covered were counted. The extent of the brush and its area on the glass slide demonstrate its spreadability.

i.e., Spreadability= $M \times L/T$

S=Spreadability

m=Weight added on the slide

l=glass slide's length

t=Time taken in seconds

5. **Irritability:** A little quantity of scrub was applied to the skin's surface and left on for a few moment.
6. **Wash ability:** A small amount of sample scrub placed on skin and pour with water and find washing property.
7. **Grittiness:** Grittiness was personally analyzed.
8. **Foam ability:** In a measuring cylinder, a small amount of scrub was stirred with and the foam was measured.
9. **Viscosity:** Brookfield viscometer is used to measure the viscosity.
10. **Stability study:** The formulation was stored for 56 days at various temperature and analyzed for colour, odour, pH and consistency.
11. **Consistency:** Visual observation was used to confirm it.

Characterization of the UV

1. TulsiSample

Determination of maximum wavelength (λ max).

Linearity curve of given tulsi sample.

Maximum wavelength of the sample was found to 281 nm.

2.Neem Sample

Determination of maximum length (λ max).

Linearity curve of given neem sample.

Maximum wavelength of the sample was found to 596 nm.

3. RESULTS :

Sr.No	Parameter	Observation
1	Colour	Greyish green
2	Odour	Pleasant
3	Nature	Semisolid gel
4	Homogeneity	Good
5	pH	5
6	Consistency	Good
7	Viscosity	1430 centipoise
8	Extrudability	Easily extrudible
9	Irritability	Non irritable
10	Wash ability	Easy washing property
11	Grittiness	Small gritty particle
12	Skin sensitivity	No rashes
13	Foamibility	250 ml at 5 min

4. Conclusion:

The formulated face scrub showed good cosmetic properties and was found to be suitable for application on human skin. Since the skin is the outermost protective layer of the body, it is continuously exposed to harmful factors such as UV radiation, chemicals, dust, and environmental pollution. Therefore, proper skin care is essential to maintain healthy skin.

In this formulation, natural ingredients were used, which helped minimize the chances of adverse effects or skin irritation. Lemon oil, a rich source of vitamin C, plays an important role in improving skin texture by making the skin soft, smooth, and refreshed. The prepared face scrub also helps in improving blood circulation and may assist in reducing acne, dark circles, and minor scars.

The formulated scrub was evaluated for various parameters including colour, odour, consistency, pH, spreadability, extrudability, viscosity, washability, irritability, and grittiness. All evaluation results were found to be satisfactory and within acceptable limits.

Hence, the developed herbal face scrub can be considered safe, effective, and beneficial for maintaining healthy, clean, and glowing skin.

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